

Play, Games and Cultural Patrimony

University of Fribourg - Workshop ERC *Locus Ludi*
May 17, 2019

After L.Becq de Fouquières, *Les jeux des Anciens*, Paris, 1869

Maison Kairos, Rue Guillaume-Techtermann 8a

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This Project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under agreement No. 741520 Locus Ludi. the Cultural Fabric of Play and Games in Classical Antiquity. Supported by the ERC Advanced Grant (2017-2022)

Programme

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Morning

Welcome Véronique Dasen (Fribourg/ERC Locus Ludi)

Chair : Fabio Spadini (Fribourg)

9h00 Ulrich Schädler (Fribourg)
Games for the dead : boardgames in tombs

9h45 Stine Schierup (Copenhagen)
Boardgames in the National Museum, Copenhagen

10h30 Break

Chair : Hanna Ammar (Fribourg)

11h00 Barbara Carè (Athens)
Game tools in burial in Magna Graecia : messages and meaning

11h45 Alexandra Attia (Fribourg)
Becq de Fouquières and South italian red-figure pottery : a story of misunderstanding ?

12h30 Lunch break

Afternoon

Chair : Marco Vespa (Fribourg)

14h00 Daniela Ventrelli (Rubi Antiqua)
Le patrimoine ludique de la Collection Jatta

14h45 Luigi La Rocca (Bari)
Archeologia in Puglia: tutela, ricerca e valorizzazione

15h30 Break

Chair : Thomas Daniaux (Fribourg)

16h00 Raffaella Cassano (Bari)
Cultura greca e mondo indigeno nella Puglia del IV e del III sec. a.C. Alcuni esempi

How to find us

09h00-17h00: Maison Kairos (aumônerie de l'Université de Fribourg)
Rue Guillaume-Techtermann 8a.

Train station > avenue de Pérolles > rue Hans Fries

